

Robot-Assisted Training Enhances Narrative Organization and Sequencing Abilities in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Randomized Controlled Trial

Ghiglino D.^{1†}, Foglino C.^{1†}, Moretti S.¹, Floris F.^{2,3}, De Tommaso D.¹, Wykowska A.^{1*}

¹ Social Cognition in Human-Robot Interaction, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova, Italy.

² Piccolo Cottolengo Genovese di Don Orione, Don Orione Italia, Genova, Italy.

³ Società Italiana Disturbi del Neurosviluppo, Firenze, Italy.

†These authors contributed equally to this work

*Corresponding author:

Agnieszka Wykowska,
Social Cognition in Human-Robot Interaction
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia,
Via E. Melen, 83
16040 Genova, Italy
Email: agnieszka.wykowska@iit.it;

Contact information:

Davide Ghiglino, davide.ghiglino@iit.it, ORCID 0000-0002-7825-732X
Foglino Caterina, caterina.foglino@iit.it, ORCID 0000-0001-7724-9363
Moretti Silvia, silvia.moretti@iit.it, ORCID 0009-0005-1277-7401
Floris Federica, federicafioris@pcdo.it, ORCID 0009-0004-3245-5365
De Tommaso Davide, davide.detommaso@iit.it, ORCID 0000-0003-2132-5261
Wykowska Agnieszka, agnieszka.wykowska@iit.it, ORCID 0000-0003-3323-7357

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Abstract

Autonomy in daily living relies on executive cognitive functions such as planning, sequencing, and monitoring of goal-directed actions, which are often compromised in children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). This study investigated whether a humanoid robot-assisted training could enhance narrative and memory abilities that serve as proxies for autonomy-related executive functions. Sixty-two children with ASD (6–15 years) participated in a two-period crossover study integrated into ongoing rehabilitation programs. Across two consecutive studies, participants alternated between robot-assisted training and standard therapy. The humanoid robot iCub mediated structured activities involving the construction of action sequences representing everyday and social routines. Narrative and executive functions were assessed using the BVSCO-3 and NEPSY-II. Data were analysed using repeated-measures ANOVAs and complementary non-parametric analyses. Robot-assisted training was associated with significant improvements in narrative production and in effortful narrative memory (Free and Cued Recall), compared with periods of standard therapy. Gains were stable over time and robust to variability in session number. Robot-assisted training embedded in clinical routines can selectively enhance narrative organization and effortful recall in children with ASD, supporting its role as a feasible scaffold for autonomy-related cognitive processes within standard therapeutic settings.

Lay Summary

Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) often find it hard to follow daily routines, stay organized, or remember steps, skills that help them do things independently. This study found that practicing these skills with a humanoid robot helped children with ASD improve more than with standard therapy alone, offering a promising way to support their independence.

Keywords: Robot-assisted intervention; Autism Spectrum Disorder; Narrative production; Executive function; Embodied interaction; Clinical rehabilitation, Robotics.

Introduction

Autonomy and independence in daily living rely on a set of executive cognitive functions, including planning, sequencing, and monitoring one's own actions. In children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), similarly to other neurodevelopmental disorders such as ADHD, Tourette syndrome, or developmental language disorders (Hill, 2004), these processes are often less efficient, limiting the ability to organize and carry out goal-directed behaviors (Robinson et al., 2009; Demetriou et al., 2018). These difficulties extend beyond the core social-communication impairments of ASD and manifest in everyday tasks such as self-care, schoolwork, and community participation, thereby restricting opportunities for autonomous functioning and independent living. Supporting the development of autonomy and independence constitutes a critical step toward adaptive functioning and quality of life in children and adolescents with developmental disabilities, including ASD (Sheppard et al., 2011; White et al., 2018).

In this regard, innovative technologies such as socially assistive robotics have emerged as promising tools that can assist therapists in clinical practice, offloading them, and providing users with the opportunity to train skills in a predictable setting allowing multiple consistent repetitions: features that are important for individuals with ASD (David et al., 2025). More specifically, humanoid robotics have opened new avenues for creating embodied scaffolds for learning (Saleh et al., 2021; Alabdulkareem et al., 2022). Humanoid robots, by physically sharing the environment, performing human-like actions, and being "proxies" for social interaction with other humans can provide consistent, predictable feedback that supports the gradual acquisition of complex skills while minimizing the sensory and emotional overload that may accompany human interactions (Alnajjar et al., 2020; Schadenberg et al., 2021).

A growing body of research consistently reports that such robots increase attention, engagement, and social responsiveness in children with ASD (Bartl-Pokorny et al., 2021; Kouroupa et al., 2022; Santos et al., 2023). Their simplified and predictable behavior provides an intermediate level of social complexity that is easier to process than human interaction, while still engaging core socio-cognitive mechanisms (Ghiglino et al., 2023; Ghiglino et al., 2025) and reducing the therapist's burden during repetitive role-play activities. Moreover, evidence from in-home interventions demonstrates that skills developed through repeated interactions with a social robot can transfer to human-directed behaviours, indicating genuine generalization beyond the robot context (Scassellati et al., 2018).

Within ASD interventions for kids, most robot-assisted interventions to date have targeted social communication and Theory of Mind skills (Takata et al., 2023; So et al., 2024), while research specifically addressing independent living skills remains limited (Sarri et al., 2021). However, the same embodied interaction principles may also be leveraged to strengthen autonomy-related competencies, such as planning and executing goal-directed actions. These functions share underlying cognitive mechanisms, like sequencing, prediction, and monitoring, with those involved in social cognition (Hill, 2004), suggesting that structured, interactive contexts that foster action organization might also promote independence in everyday life.

Our study investigated whether humanoid-assisted training can enhance autonomy-related skills in children with ASD. The intervention integrated robot-mediated activities within established rehabilitation programs, using the humanoid robot iCub (Metta et al., 2010). This design extends prior work in which the same robot successfully scaffolded social skills, such as

Theory of Mind and joint attention, through visual perspective taking (Ghiglino et al., 2023) and role-play scenarios (Ghiglino et al., 2025).

For the present study, in collaboration with clinical professionals, we implemented a two-period crossover design where two groups of children underwent robot-assisted and standard therapy phases, in counterbalanced order across groups. The robot-mediated sessions involved turn-taking with the robot to build action sequences using illustrated cubes depicting daily routines (e.g. making orange juice) or social scenarios (e.g. taking public transportation), thereby promoting temporal and causal organization of actions. To assess improvements, we administered standardized neuropsychological tests targeting narrative and executive abilities, two domains closely related to the development of autonomous functioning, as they both rely on the capacity to plan, organize, and monitor goal-directed actions. Specifically, we used the BVSCO-3 test (Cornoldi et al., 2022), focusing on the Written Narrative Production task, in which children must order a sequence of pictures and produce a coherent written story. Because this task requires planning, structuring ideas, and monitoring one's output, it was employed here as a proxy for planning and monitoring processes involved in autonomous behavior (e.g. deciding the sequence of actions needed to complete a task, such as preparing food). In addition, to investigate cross-domain cognitive effects, we included the NEPSY-II (Korkman et al., 2007) Narrative Memory subscale, which probes memory and attention, crucial mechanisms for proper functioning in daily life, as they enable individuals to retain relevant information, stay focused on ongoing tasks, and manage competing demands.

We hypothesized that both robot-assisted training and standard therapy would enhance children's ability to plan and recall action sequences, reflecting general improvements in autonomy-related skills. However, we expected stronger and broader effects in the robot-assisted condition, due to the humanoid's predictable and engaging interaction style and in line with previous results (Ghiglino et al., 2025). Such findings would suggest that humanoid robots can act as embodied scaffolds for the development of skills necessary for autonomy in daily living, potentially complementing traditional clinical approaches.

Methods

Participants

A total of sixty-two children, aged between six and fifteen years, took part in the study. All participants completed both parts of the project, which was organized as two consecutive intervention periods—Study 1 and Study 2—each study involving a standard and robot-assisted training (counterbalanced across studies). This arrangement meant that every child contributed data twice, once while receiving the robot-assisted training and once while receiving only standard therapy, allowing each participant to act both as an experimental case and as a passive control at different points in time. However, Study 1 differed from Study 2 in that the robot-assisted part of Study 1 involved sequencing of actions for daily routines (e.g., preparing an orange juice) while in Study 2 it was centred around more social activities (e.g., taking public transportation).

The two studies were based on an iterative, clinician-led refinement of the protocol. After Study 1, a therapist focus group reported that children quickly mastered the self-care routines and would benefit from greater cognitive, social, and contextual complexity. Accordingly, before Study 2 the protocol was adapted to include socially oriented scenarios, structured distractors, and deliberate robot errors. This iterative co-design process is not the focus of the present paper

but explains why the two studies share a similar structure while differing in content and complexity of the training protocols.

All children had a confirmed diagnosis of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), validated independently by the Italian National Health Service (Servizio Sanitario Nazionale, SSN) and by the clinical institution hosting the study, the Piccolo Cottolengo Genovese di Don Orione – Centro Boggiano Pico in Genova. Diagnostic procedures followed standardized protocols, including administration of the ADI-R (Lord, Rutter, & Le Couteur, 1994) and the ADOS-2 (Lord et al., 2012) carried out by licensed clinicians specializing in developmental disorders.

Participants were randomly assigned to two groups. Participants were allocated by the treating clinician using a constrained, non-random assignment procedure to ensure approximate balance in age and gender across sequences; investigators had no control over allocation, outcome assessors were blinded, and full randomization was not feasible due to clinical and rehabilitative priorities within this vulnerable population. The first group consisted of twenty-nine children (mean age = 10.66 ± 1.82 years; IQ = 74.28 ± 20.54 ; nine females), and the second group consisted of thirty-three children (mean age = 9.49 ± 2.44 years; IQ = 80.30 ± 24.55 ; five females). These groups alternated their roles across the two studies: between T0 and T1 (Study 1) the first group received the robot-assisted training for daily routines while the second group continued with standard therapy, whereas between T1 and T2 (Study 2) the second group received the robot-assisted training for social activities and the first group received standard therapy (acting as passive control, see Figure 1). Note that we accounted for age-based subgroup effects in an additional analysis (cf. Supplementary Materials, Section S5) which showed that our results reported in main text below were robust and generalizable across our age range (6-15 years).

Figure 1. CONSORT flow diagram illustrating participant enrolment, randomization, allocation, follow-up, and analysis for Study 1 and Study 2.

The adequacy of the sample size was evaluated a priori through power analysis for a two-group crossover design with pre–post measurements, assuming a large standardized effect, two-tailed testing, and an α level of .05. Based on both these estimates and previous robot-assisted intervention studies reporting significant effects with samples of approximately 20 participants per group, an initial target of at least 40 participants overall was considered sufficient. The final sample size (29 and 33 participants per sequence) was therefore deemed adequate to ensure acceptable statistical power ($\geq .80$) for detecting large intervention effects.

Recruitment took place through the clinical staff during regular therapy sessions, where families were informed about the project and invited to participate. Inclusion criteria were intentionally broad, requiring only that children were able to understand the task instructions and that

caregivers consented to participation. Written informed consent was obtained from both parents or from legal guardians. The study was approved by the Comitato Etico Regione Liguria and conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. No participants withdrew, and no data were removed due to discomfort, non-compliance, or other adverse responses.

Standard therapy

All participants continued their standard therapy at the rehabilitation center, based on Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) principles and other evidence-based practices recommended by national guidelines. For more details see Supplementary Materials, see Section S1.

Robot-Assisted Training Protocol

The robot-assisted training protocol was jointly developed by the research team at the Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia and the clinical staff of the Piccolo Cottolengo Genovese di Don Orione – Centro Boggiano Pico (Genova, Italy), within the framework of the ERC-funded Proof-of-Concept RONIN project (RObot traINing INdependence). Participants first completed Study 1 between T0 and T1, and subsequently completed Study 2 between T1 and T2. Because of the crossover design, the two groups alternated between receiving the robot-assisted protocol and the standard therapy during these two studies (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Crossover structure of the intervention. In Study 1, Group 1 received the Robot-assisted training on *Self-care and Everyday Autonomy*, while Group 2 received Standard therapy between T0 and T1. Subsequently, in Study 2, the groups switched roles: Group 1 received Standard therapy, and Group 2 completed the Robot-assisted training focused on *Social Autonomy and Error Detection* between T1 and T2.

Across both studies, sessions took place inside the clinical facilities of the rehabilitation centre. The child sat at a table directly facing the humanoid robot iCub (approximately 104 cm tall) placed across the table from the child, separated by a transparent plexiglass panel to ensure safety. The robot was operated in Wizard-of-Oz mode by a research assistant seated in the same room but outside the child’s visual field, while a clinician, seated next to the child undergoing training, supervised each session to ensure comfort and adherence to therapeutic goals. The foundational structure of each session remained constant across the two studies: the robot greeted the child, introduced the activity, and engaged in a turn-taking task in which the child and the robot collaboratively constructed short sequences of actions exchanging cubes to which pictures representing various actions were attached. Each session included two complete collaborative sequences, usually lasting between fifteen and twenty minutes. The child initiated the first sequence, and the robot initiated the second, maintaining a balance between structure and autonomy. In child-initiated sequences, the child chose the first action depicted on one of the cubes (upon the robot’s prompt), placed the selected cube into a small wheeled tray and pushed it toward the robot, which “inspected” it and gave standardized feedback (“correct”/“try again”). The robot then selected the second action and passed the cube through the wheeled

tray, and the child completed the sequence by exchanging the final cube. In robot-initiated sequences, the robot chose the first and last actions, and the child selected the second one, following the same structure. After each cube exchange - cubes handed to the robot were always returned to the child - the child positioned the chosen action into a numbered sequence holder (see Figure 3). Verbal feedback from the robot remained standardized across all sessions, allowing consistency in the interaction. At the end of each sequence, the child was asked to verbally describe the routine they had constructed.

Figure 3. *Robot-Assisted Training Protocol.* The child positions the next action in the sequence placing the illustrated cube into the numbered sequence holder (indicated by the red arrow in the figure), while a clinician supervises the interaction. Note that the plexiglass divider that was placed in-between the child and the robot during training sessions was temporarily removed for illustration purposes to avoid reflections in the photograph.

All cubes were composed of soft polyurethane (10×10×10 cm) and displayed removable Velcro-backed stickers depicting single actions. A visual example of the setup and the Wizard-of-Oz teleoperation is presented in Figure 4, which illustrates the research assistant controlling the robot's behaviors in real time from a concealed position within the room.

Figure 4. *Wizard-of-Oz teleoperation setup used during the robot-assisted training.* The research assistant (upper panel) controls the humanoid robot iCub remotely through a dedicated interface (lower panel) while seated in the same room but outside the participant's view. This Wizard-of-Oz configuration allows the robot to appear autonomous to the child, while its verbal and motor behaviours are manually triggered by the research assistant in real time to ensure smooth, context-appropriate interaction.

Study 1: Self-Care and Autonomy in Daily Routines (T0 – T1)

Study 1 implemented the first version of the protocol, focusing on action planning within familiar self-care and everyday routines. This version emphasized temporal sequencing, causal coherence, and the execution of multi-step goal-directed actions. In this study, Group 1 of participants received the robot-assisted training, while Group 2 continued standard therapy. Over approximately eight weeks, children collaboratively worked through routines such as washing hands, taking a shower, choosing clothes based on weather conditions, preparing orange juice (see Figure 5), selecting food from a fridge, buying an item from a vending machine, packing for short trips (mountain, beach, or city), and cooking pasta. The robot followed a structured verbal script to introduce each activity, maintaining predictable timing and intonation to support comprehension. Each child typically attended around six sessions (from a minimum of 3 to a maximum of 10), depending on their clinical schedule. Note that we accounted for variability in the number of sessions across participants in an additional analysis (cf. Supplementary Materials, Section S4) which showed that our results reported in main text below were stable across variable number of training sessions. This study functioned as a structured, visually grounded sequence-building activity designed to strengthen planning, monitoring, and hierarchical organization of action. Because Group 1 received this version of the training first, its improvements between T0 and T1 reflect exclusively the effects of this Study 1 protocol.

Figure 5. Example of Self-Care and Everyday Autonomy sticker sequence used in Study 1. The illustrated panels depict the steps involved in making orange juice: Children were asked to arrange these steps in the correct order to form a coherent sequence together with the robot.

Study 2: Social Autonomy and Error Detection (T1 – T2)

Study 2 implemented a second, more cognitively demanding version of the protocol, based on feedback from therapists during focus groups after Study 1. While maintaining the same physical setup and general session structure as in Study 1, this version introduced distractor stimuli and deliberate robot errors (for detailed description, see paragraph below), designed to increase the cognitive and social complexity of the task. In this study, Group 2 received the robot-assisted training, whereas Group 1 continued with standard therapy. The first two sessions served as familiarization and involved action sequences without distractors. From the third session onward, distractor-based errors were introduced (one per session). In these sessions, routines were extended to four cubes and included distractor stickers marked with red edges. These distractor-based sessions were implemented in two versions using the same stickers. In the first version, the operator controlling iCub deliberately selected a distractor sticker and inserted it into the collaborative sequence as if it were the correct next action. This behaviour was explicitly designed and programmed—it did not reflect mechanical malfunction—and its purpose was to create a socially meaningful opportunity for the child to detect and correct the robot’s mistake. This required children to anticipate the correct continuation of the routine, monitor their partner’s actions, identify inconsistencies, and signal the mistake, providing a structured context for practicing metacognitive monitoring, causal reasoning, and socially mediated error correction. In the second version, the child – rather than the robot – selected the next action, with a plausible but incorrect distractor presented among the options, assessing the ability to ignore irrelevant information rather than monitoring the robot behavior. The content of Study 2 also differed from Study 1, focusing on more complex community-based and social scenarios. These included taking public transportation (see Figure 6), shopping, going to the cinema, helping another in distress, practising fire-evacuation routines at school, participating in a dance recital, organizing a social event with peers, and managing unexpected situations such as getting lost in a store. The robot’s verbal script was intentionally simplified to support a faster interaction rhythm, while still maintaining a predictable turn-taking structure. Each child completed between eight and ten sessions over approximately ten weeks, depending on their clinical attendance pattern. This second version of the protocol therefore placed greater demands on the child’s ability to evaluate contextual appropriateness, detect partner errors, and maintain goal-oriented behaviour despite distractors. Because Group 2 completed this sequence between T1 and T2, improvements in this interval specifically correspond to the cognitive and functional impact of the Study 2 design.

Figure 6. Example of a Social Autonomy and Error Detection sequence used in Study 2. The illustrated panels depict the steps involved in taking public transportation with a distractor present: (1) a child using crutches boards the bus, (2a) one child (green t-shirt) offers their seat, (2b) the same child fails to offer their seat, and (3) the child with crutches sits down. Children were asked either to identify the incorrect action (2b) and select the appropriate alternative (2a) to complete the sequence, or to recognise when the robot had incorrectly chosen the distractor. Both distractor implementations were designed to engage children’s ability to recognise the greater need of the child using crutches within this social context.

Measures of interest

Participants completed standardized neuropsychological assessments before and after the intervention to evaluate cognitive and functional effects of the training. Specifically, Written Narrative Production subtest of the BVSCO-3 test was used. This sub-test requires organizing and structuring a coherent narrative and is theoretically linked to executive functions and metacognitive processes underpinning autonomous behavior (Cornoldi et al., 2010). Performance on this task was therefore interpreted as an index of the ability to plan, integrate, and regulate goal-directed output. To examine possible cross-domain effects, verbal memory and related executive processes were assessed using the Narrative Memory subtest of the NEPSY-II (Free and Cued Recall for all participants; Recognition Recall for younger children only). Both measures were administered at baseline (T0), after the first intervention phase (T1), and after the second phase (T2) by examiners blind to treatment condition. Raw scores were standardized using age-based norms. Additional methodological and theoretical details are provided in the Supplementary Materials (see section S2).

Analyses

We analysed the scores obtained from the Narration task of the BVSCO-3 and the narrative memory subtests of the NEPSY-II across the three assessment time points (T0, T1, and T2) in both experimental groups, across the two studies.

Given that the NEPSY-II tasks, in particular, are closely related to general cognitive abilities, we first conducted correlation analyses between IQ (measured using the WISC) and our dependent variables, to determine whether any results should be adjusted and to control for the potential influence of participants’ specific cognitive skills on performance outcomes.

We observed that IQ at T0 was significantly correlated with all three NEPSY-II subscales (Free Recall: $r = 0.56$, $p < .001$; Cued Recall: $r = 0.60$, $p < .001$; Recognition: $r = 0.75$, $p < .001$), whereas no correlation was found with the BVSCO-3 Narration score ($r = 0.04$, $p = .788$). For this reason, IQ was included as a covariate in the analyses involving NEPSY-II scores, to control for potential confounding effects.

For each of our dependent variables, we conducted separate repeated-measures ANOVAs, providing a comprehensive view of the data. Prior to each analysis, we verified the assumptions: data homogeneity was always met ($p > .05$), whereas sphericity was generally violated (for BVSCO: Mauchly's $W = 0.71$, $p < .001$; for NEPSY-II Free Recall: $W = 0.61$, $p < .001$; for Cued Recall: $W = 0.83$, $p = .013$), except for NEPSY-II Recognition ($W = 0.93$, $p = .894$). To account for the lack of sphericity, the Huynh–Feldt correction was applied to all ANOVAs. For each effect detected, the F , p , and η_p^2 values are reported as measures of effect size. Following each main analysis, we performed post hoc tests exploring the Group \times Time interaction, to better understand which pairwise comparisons drove the main and interaction effects. Given the number of comparisons performed, Bonferroni correction was applied to control for Type I error risk. For each post hoc test, the corresponding t value and corrected p value are reported.

We conducted further non-parametric analyses on delta-scores for both studies, to give the reader another intuitive summary of the changes within each study, and to account for variability in the number of robot-assisted sessions. The analyses description and results are reported in the Supplementary Material (see sections S3, S4 and S5). All analyses were performed using JASP software (version 18.0.0) and figures were generated using R Studio.

Results

In addition to the quantitative measures reported in the following sections, qualitative observations were collected throughout both studies by the research assistant teleoperating the robot. The observations indicated good tolerability and engagement across age groups and are reported in the Supplementary Materials (see section S6).

BVSCO-3 – Narrative abilities

Data analysis revealed a significant Group \times Time interaction ($F_{(1, 48)} = 8.47$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.15$) and a significant main effect of Time ($F_{(1, 48)} = 30.85$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.39$), but no significant main effect of Group ($F_{(1, 48)} = 0.11$, $p = .753$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.002$). Post hoc analyses confirmed that there were no differences between groups at baseline ($t_{49} = -0.97$, $p = 1.00$), allowing for separate within-group analyses.

In Group 1 (G1)—the group that completed the robot-assisted activities between T0 and T1—a significant improvement was observed between T0 and T1 ($t_{24} = -6.40$, $p < .001$), which was maintained at T2, as indicated by the continued difference between T0 and T2 ($t_{24} = -6.80$, $p < .001$) and the absence of a significant difference between T1 and T2 ($t_{24} = -0.40$, $p = 1.00$). This pattern suggests that the gains achieved during the first training phase were stable over time.

Conversely, in Group 2 (G2), which served as the passive control between T0 and T1, no significant change was detected during that period ($t_{26} = -0.72$, $p = 1.00$). However, a significant improvement emerged between T1 and T2 ($t_{26} = -3.35$, $p = .017$), when G2 participated in the robot-assisted activities. This effect was further supported by a significant difference between T0 and T2 within the same group ($t_{26} = -4.07$, $p = .001$) (see Figure 7).

BVSCO-3 Scores (Narration Task)

Figure 7. Standardized BVSCO-3 narrative scores for Group 1 (G1) and Group 2 (G2) across the three assessment timepoints. T0–T1 corresponds to Study 1, during which G1 received the robot-assisted training and G2 served as the passive control; T1–T2 corresponds to Study 2, during which the roles were reversed and G2 received the robot-assisted training while G1 served as the passive control. Individual trajectories are represented by thin lines, and boxplots summarize the distribution at each timepoint.

NEPSY-II – Narrative Memory

Free recall

Analysis of the Free Recall scores revealed a significant Group \times Time interaction ($F(1, 49) = 4.08$, $p = .032$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.08$) and a significant main effect of Group ($F(1, 49) = 4.10$, $p = .048$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.08$), whereas the main effect of Time was not significant ($F(1, 49) = 0.17$, $p = .780$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.003$). At baseline, the two groups did not differ significantly ($t_{51} = 1.06$, $p = 1.00$), allowing for separate within-group comparisons. In Group 1 (G1), which underwent the robot-assisted training between T0 and T1, performance significantly improved from T0 to T1 ($t_{25} = -4.06$, $p = .001$) and from T0 to T2 ($t_{25} = -4.53$, $p < .001$), with no difference between T1 and T2 ($t_{25} = -0.47$, $p = 1.00$), indicating that gains were maintained over time. In contrast, Group 2 (G2)—serving as the passive control during the first period—showed no significant differences between T0 and T1 ($t_{27} = -0.08$, $p = 1.00$), T0 and T2 ($t_{27} = -2.50$, $p = .209$), or T1 and T2 ($t_{27} = -2.43$, $p = .256$). These results suggest that only G1, the group exposed to the robot-assisted training first, exhibited measurable improvement in Free Recall performance (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. NEPSY-II Free Recall scalar scores for Group 1 (G1) and Group 2 (G2) across the three timepoints. As in Figure N1, T0–T1 represents Study 1 with G1 in the experimental condition and G2 in the control condition, whereas T1–T2 represents Study 2 with G2 receiving the robot-assisted training and G1 serving as the control. Individual trajectories and boxplots depict within-group variability and change across time.

Cued recall

A comparable pattern emerged for the Cued Recall subscale. The analysis yielded a significant Group \times Time interaction ($F(1, 49) = 5.77, p = .006, \eta_p^2 = 0.11$), whereas neither the main effect of Time ($F(1, 49) = 0.11, p = .873, \eta_p^2 = 0.002$) nor that of Group ($F(1, 49) = 3.57, p = .065, \eta_p^2 = 0.07$) reached significance. Given the significant interaction and the trend toward a group effect, post-hoc comparisons were performed. As in the Free Recall condition, G1 showed significant gains from T0 to T1 ($t_{25} = -4.51, p < .001$) and from T0 to T2 ($t_{25} = -4.77, p < .001$), with stability between T1 and T2 ($t_{25} = -0.26, p = 1.00$). In G2, no significant differences were found across any of the timepoints (T0–T1: $t_{27} = 0.13, p = 1.00$; T0–T2: $t_{27} = -1.58, p = 1.00$; T1–T2: $t_{27} = 2.01, p = .726$). Thus, the improvements in Cued Recall were confined to G1 following its exposure to the robot-based activities, with no observable changes in the control group (see Figure 9).

NEPSY-II Scalar Scores (Cued Recall)

Figure 9. NEPSY-II Cued Recall scalar scores for Group 1 (G1) and Group 2 (G2) across T0, T1, and T2. The structural interpretation of the timeline mirrors Figures N1 and N2: G1 was the experimental group during Study 1 (T0–T1), and G2 was the experimental group during Study 2 (T1–T2). Thin lines show individual change over time, and boxplots indicate the distribution at each assessment.

Recognition

For the Recognition subscale, the analysis did not reveal any significant effects. Neither the main effect of Time ($F(1, 34) = 2.95, p = .059, \eta_p^2 = 0.08$) nor the main effect of Group ($F(1, 34) = 1.26, p = .270, \eta_p^2 = 0.04$) reached significance, and there was no significant Group \times Time interaction ($F(1, 34) = 1.19, p = .311, \eta_p^2 = 0.03$). Given the absence of meaningful effects, no further post-hoc analyses were conducted for this measure.

To complement the repeated-measures ANOVA, we compared the change scores across different measurement points (T0, T1, T2) with non-parametric statistical tests. These are reported in Supplementary Materials (Section S3).

Discussion

The present study investigated whether a robot-assisted training could enhance autonomy-related skills in children with ASD through structured, embodied interaction embedded within routine clinical sessions. By combining action sequencing and distractor identification within daily and social scenarios, the intervention aimed to scaffold executive functions, such as planning, sequencing, and monitoring, that are crucial for independent functioning in daily life. To address the aims of our study, we recruited two groups of children diagnosed with ASD. Both groups exhibited significant gains in the BVSCO-3 Narrative Production task following the intervention with the humanoid robot iCub, reflecting enhanced ability to plan, organize, and verbally describe goal-directed sequences of actions. These improvements were maintained over time and were not observed in the passive control group, supporting the hypothesis that robot-mediated activities promoted transferable autonomy-related skills.

Performance on the NEPSY-II Narrative Memory subtest, administered to explore potential cross-domain cognitive effects of the training, revealed a more selective pattern. Significant improvements emerged only for the Free and Cued Recall conditions in Group 1 following robot-assisted training, whereas no changes were observed in Group 2, either after the passive control or robot-intervention phases. Moreover, no effects were shown in the Recognition condition in either groups of participants, possibly indicating that the robot-assisted training facilitated the active organization and retrieval of verbal narrative content only under conditions requiring effortful reconstruction and guided recall, but not in recognition.

The specificity of the NEPSY-II results suggests that the cross-domain transfer of the training may rely on characteristics of the intervention. Study 1, which focused on self-care and everyday routines, may have provided a stronger structural analogue to the narrative recall task, as it requires temporal and causal organization of sequential information. Conversely, Study 2 emphasized error detection, distractor inhibition, and social reasoning, thus engaging metacognitive monitoring more than linear narrative construction. Moreover, the content of training for Group 1 was slightly less complex than for Group 2. One possible explanation of the pattern of results could be that improvements in recall tasks are more likely when training is not too cognitively demanding. This speculative interpretation would need to be tested in future research. Taken together, these findings suggest that while the robot-assisted training can promote structured verbal organization and retrieval, its broader benefits for verbal memory processes may depend on the content and cognitive demands of the activities implemented.

These results extend prior evidence showing that socially assistive robots can improve social communication and Theory of Mind (Ghiglino et al., 2021, 2023, 2025; Takata et al., 2023; So et al., 2024) by demonstrating that similar embodied interaction principles can foster autonomy-related skills. The iCub's predictable, human-like feedback and turn-taking behaviours appear to have provided a stable and socially meaningful scaffold, helping children organize and monitor actions within a collaborative context. This pattern aligns with previous evidence showing that structured, visually supported activities (Hume et al., 2014; Sreckovic et al., 2020) and predictable social environments (Schadenberg et al., 2021) facilitate executive functioning and task initiation in ASD. Therefore, these results support the emerging view that embodied social interaction with robots may offer a promising medium for strengthening executive functions and autonomy-related skills. Furthermore, the inclusion of distractor elements and deliberate robot "errors" in Study 2 may have further strengthened children's metacognitive monitoring. Qualitative observations from therapists and teleoperators support this interpretation: children showed increasing engagement, empathy, and self-correction behaviours, indicating that the robot was not merely a stimulus but a social partner. The improvement in narrative and memory performance suggests that robot-assisted training may generalize beyond immediate task learning to higher-order cognitive functions. Narrative organization tasks, such as those used in the BVSCO-3 and NEPSY-II, require coordination of executive and linguistic resources to construct temporally coherent representations. Enhanced performance in these domains may therefore reflect a more general improvement in planning, working memory, and sequencing abilities, which are essential components of functional independence (Hill, 2004; Demetriou et al., 2018).

From a clinical standpoint, the results support the feasibility and added value of integrating humanoid robots into existing therapeutic frameworks. The intervention was well-tolerated, elicited positive affect, and maintained children's motivation across multiple weeks. Therapists likewise reported a positive impression and smooth integration of the intervention within the

clinical activities. The robot's capacity to deliver consistent prompts without fatigue may help reduce adult-mediated prompting, addressing one of the key barriers to generalization identified in traditional interventions (Hume et al., 2014; Sreckovic et al., 2020). Moreover, by collaboratively building and organizing sequences of everyday actions, the iCub robot provided a concrete and engaging way for children to practise planning and structuring routines, effectively bridging visual supports and guided practice within an embodied-learning framework.

Limitations and future directions

Some methodological limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study did not include an active control group, although the crossover design partly addressed this by allowing each group to serve as its own control across studies. Second, the sample heterogeneity in age and cognitive level may have contributed to variability in outcomes. Future studies should examine more homogeneous subgroups or use larger samples allowing for cluster analyses to identify profiles of greater responsiveness. Finally, the teleoperation of the robot (Wizard-of-Oz) ensured safety and adaptability during the intervention, but limited automation. Future studies could test adaptive autonomous robot behaviours to increase clinical applicability and ecological realism.

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